

H2020 Work Programme

D4.3 – Report on results of the capacity building workshop

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This document is the outcome of BIObec project related to the Report on results of the capacity building workshop (contract no. 101023381) corresponding to D4.3 (M30) led by CTA. This document contains the summary of the activities conducted and the results of the workshop collected through Task 4.3.

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1. Acronyms and abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
DOA	Description of the Action
IRWG	Implementation and Replication Working Group
GP	General Public
BBEC	Bio-Based Education Centre
WP	Work Package
UNIBO	Alma-Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna
CTA	Fundación Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía
SIE	Sustainable Innovations
FVA	FVA New Media Research
CBU JU	Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

2. Executive summary

This report summarises the methodology used for the design, the analysis and the main aspects achieved during the BIObec capacity building.

The workshop was designed to increase the capacitation of stakeholders interested in the implementation and replication of Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs) under the vision of the BIObec project partners. The workshop is the result of the Task 4.3 but is fed by the implementation of all the other WP4 tasks, in particular Tasks 4.1 and 4.2, and the results of all WPs. At the same time, the outcomes of the event are part of the e-learning material developed in the Task 4.4, reported on D4.4.

To this end, the workshop was promoted intensively, mainly through personal communication. In order to maximise synergies and impact, WP4 and WP5 leaders decided, in agreement with the Project Officer, to hold an online meeting back-to-back with the 2nd International IRWG workshop. Therefore, the final target audience was the general audience enhanced with the participation of our Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG), which includes a variety of stakeholders with the bioeconomy as the main common factor. In addition, both workshops were disseminated in several European bioeconomy platforms and promoted during different meetings in which the BIObec partners participated, arising a strong public interested towards BIObec project and its final activities.

The workshops were structured into 5 sections, 3 of them focused on BIObec replication methodology, BIObec e-learning materials and BIObec exploitation assets. We think that the organisation of capacity building workshop back-to-back with the 2nd International IRWG improved the capacitation experience because it offered a holistic perspective of the BIObec project (Section 3.4 for further details). On one hand, the methodology for the replication was explored in depth, supported by online tools and materials enhancing the interactivity and comprehension by the final users of the results produced during the project. On the other hand, both workshops complemented each other reinforcing technical aspect with a more practical perspective based on the exploitation plan generated. This offered the possibility of exploring the assets identified, that might speed up the process of implementing new BBECs. In total, the workshop reached to 57 participants of which 35 participants were not BIObec partners, belonging mainly to academy and public administration. These 35 participants showed a geographic coverage that differed at local or regional location from the six pilot BBECs, although these differences are less pronounced at country level.

With the accomplishment of the main objective of Task 4.3, the project is now ready to transfer the methodology to stakeholders that will potentially contribute to the implementation and replication of BBECs after the end of BIObec.

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3. Introduction

3.1. BIObec objectives

The main aim of the BIObec project is to develop a comprehensive approach for multi-level Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs). In the point of view of the consortium, the BBECs should answer the present and future needs of the industry demands in a flexible pathway and taking into account the surrounding environment at local, regional, national and/or international contexts. To this end, we have initiated six BBECs pilots' programs, strategically dispersed across Europe to ensure broad geographic coverage and addressing different thematic linked to the variety of the value chains and institutional context. BIObec project has clarified the needs of the regional ecosystems, provided a detailed design, economic and financial assessment; governance plans for the educational training centres as well as plans for life-long-learning programmes. As consequence of BIObec project implementation, the consortium has developed collaborative tools to maximize the synergies between them at the European and international level.

3.2. WP4 objectives

The main objective of WP4 is to provide a roll-out strategy and a roadmap for coordinating the replication of BBECs at European and/or international level, fostering the outcomes exploitation and collaborations. Therefore, the WP4 specific objectives are:

- The identification of collaborations and synergies among BIObec BBECs and provide a meeting forum to them.
- The design of a roadmap for collaboration and replication.
- The development of a capacity building tool for collaboration and replication.
- The generation of support material for collaboration and replication.
- The design of a standard and certification scheme to support collaboration and replication.

3.3. Task 4.3 objective

Specifically, Task 4.3 aim is:

- To transfer the BIObec methodology toward implementation of regional BBECs in other regions or countries.

In order to support the replication and roll-out of the BIObec outputs in regions not involved in the project, a capacity building workshop has been organized and the current report has been prepared.

3.4. Deviation on initial plan

After careful consideration within the consortium, it was decided to modify the initial plan for the capacity building workshop originally scheduled to be organized by CTA in M28 (December 2023), in a central location and potentially as parallel workshop of a bioeconomy event of interest. These adjustments were prompted by several factors, including the challenges associated with hosting an in-person workshop in the month of December. In agreement with the Project Officer and the BIObec Coordinator, the format was consequently changed to an online setting, allowing for wider participation, mitigating logistical constraints and the event was finally postponed to January.

As a strategy to maximise the impact of the capacity building workshop, it was decided to show not only the transfer methodology for the implementation and replication of BBECs and the e-learning materials generated (D4.4), but also the identified exploitable assets ready for application by the education community, as part of the 2nd international IRWG workshop foreseen under WP5. This format was fine-tuned after the implementation of the “BIObec BBECs roadmap co-design experience and cross-fertilisation seminar”, which took place in Vienna on September 6th, 2023. This seminar was in fact a preliminary capacity building workshop and was opened to a wider audience than initially planned. In this context, the inclusion of the pathway experience of the different BBECs caught the attention of the audience. It was therefore felt that the capacity building workshop was seen as an opportunity not only to provide a methodology for replication, but also to offer a practical perspective on the available exploitable assets detected. Therefore, the organisation in the same day of both workshops could strengthen the experience and engagement of stakeholders. The organisation back-to-back of the capacity building workshop (WP4) and the 2nd international IRWG (WP5) was considered as the most effective solution to also avoid the risk of the potential audience attrition with multiple events in a short period of time. Furthermore, it was considered that the audience would be effectively empowered by giving both a holistic view of the results of WP4, and the mutual synergies generated together WP5.

Bio-based Industries
Consortium

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4. Methodology

To guarantee a diverse and engaged audience, specific guidelines were established, outlining the responsibilities as follows:

- Each BBEC leader was tasked with disseminating of the event by sending the agenda and invitations by **personal communication** to potential participants in the event.
- BIObec partners were kindly requested to share the agenda, invite attendees, and promote the event as much as possible.
- BIObec social media channels supported the event.

The primary target of the capacity building workshop was the broader audience possible sharing an interest in the development of bioeconomy education. As the 2nd International IRWG workshop was hold the same day, the regional IRWG members of the six pilot BBECs were also invited.

4.1 Official event title

The workshop was officially named as “**BIObec Capacity Building and 2nd International IRWG Workshop**”. This is the result of integrating of the capacity building (WP4) and the second international IRWG workshops (WP5) into a single day, with the aim of reinforcing possible synergies and providing the audience with a more complete experience, towards the implementation and exploitation of the results.

4.2 Workshop objectives

The BIObec consortium had specific objectives during the organisation of the workshop:

- Support the replication and roll-out of BIObec outputs beyond the regions covered by the BIObec project.
- Record the workshop for the inclusion in the e-learning materials developed in Task 4.4 (D4.4).

4.3 Agenda

The workshop was structured into five sections:

- Welcome and introduction.
- Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BIObec roadmap.
- BIObec's E-Learning Materials: Empowering Education in Bioeconomy.
- 2nd International IRWG workshop, in which the main exploitable assets and tools were presented to the audience.
- Closing remarks and questions session.

Table 1. Final Agenda

January 22 nd , 2024		
10:00-10:10	Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to BIObec and objectives of the day 	Davide Viaggi UNIBO
10:10-11:10	Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BIObec roadmap <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transferring of methodology for the replication of BBEC in external regions. 	Rafael Dueñas-Sánchez FCTA
11:10-11:30	BIObec's E-Learning Materials: Empowering Education in Bioeconomy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting material presents in BIObec website 	Daniel Matilla SIE
11:30-11:40	Break	
11:40-12:10	2nd International IRWG workshop <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the main exploitable assets and tools from BIObec results to empower IRWG members in the replication of BBECs 	Selenia Marinelli FVA
12:10-12:15	Closing remarks and networking session	Davide Viaggi All partners

The workshop has been conducted in English, with collaborative efforts from four consortium partners involved in WP4 and WP5. UNIBO as the coordinator of the BIObec project, SIE as the developer of the e-learning materials, FVA as WP5 leader and responsible for the development of the BIObec exploitation plan, as well as the organisation of the 2nd international IRWG workshop, and CTA as WP4 leader, responsible of the development of the replication methodology and organiser of the capacity building workshop.

4.4 Potential attendees

The main target audience was the general public interested in bioeconomy education at all levels, from vocational education to university, as well as educators in lifelong learning. Moreover, due to the organisation in the same day with the 2nd international IRWG workshop, the regional IRWG members of the BIObec project were also invited to ensure a diversity of profiles from the quadruple helix. As mentioned above, the invitations were sent by personal emails by the consortium members. CTA provided them with an email template, an explanation of the event and an agenda with the proposal to facilitate their engagement. An example of the email that was sent is provided below so that the partners could adapt it to the local language, etc.

“Dear Mr./Ms.:

the BIObec project (<https://biobec.eu/>) is entering the final stretch of its execution. Therefore, it is ready to present its results to various stakeholders, especially in the bioeconomy education sector. This project aims to develop a holistic framework for multi-level Bio-Based Education Centers (BBEC) focused on promoting bioeconomy education to bridge the gap between the bio-industry and the education system.

The consortium would like to invite you to the capacity building and 2nd international meeting of the Implementation and Replication Working Group, which will take place on 22 January 2024 online (Please, find the registration link to the event in the agenda file). The workshop has two main objectives: the transfer of the BIObec methodology for the implementation and replication of regional BBECs in other regions or countries, as well as of educational contents and exploitable assets ready to be implemented by the education community.

The workshop, which will be recorded, is aimed at those interested in promoting bioeconomy education in their regions. It will therefore be a learning activity to provide recommendations and practical guidelines that will be consolidated in the final toolkit of the BIObec project.

Yours sincerely,”

Towards the end of the BIObec project, partners carried out up to three activities just few days away from each other, such as the **BIObec webinar for international students** on January 17th, the **BIObec capacity building and 2nd international IRWG** on January 22nd and the **BIObec final conference** on January 30th. Therefore, coordination between the different partners has been essential to avoid overlapping of content and to prevent overloading the participants with multiple activities.

4.5 Social media and promotional actions

To extend our reach to a more diverse audience, especially outside the BIObec partners' locations, BIObec conducted a social media campaign and various promotional activities in parallel with the personal contact.

The BIObec capacity building and 2nd International IRWG workshop were promoted mainly in LinkedIn and X through the official channel (Figure 1). It was kindly asked to the consortium members to further disseminate the event from their own personal profiles, as well as their institutional accounts, to reach to the maximum audience possible.

Figure 1-. Promotional poster used in social media.

In addition to social media, the workshop was disseminated through posts on several digital platforms such as the European Cluster Collaboration Platform (ECCP) a European online hub for cluster stakeholders with an active community and the European Bioeconomy Network, which counts more than 150 EU funded projects and initiatives involved in bioeconomy. It was also disseminated by CTA channels: social media and CTA newsletter that has more than 6600 subscribers. Furthermore, it was promoted at the CBE JU Stakeholder Forum held on December 7th, 2023 in Brussels, Belgium (see D5.9 for a more extensive report). This forum attracted over 400 attendees from more than 30 countries, and BIObec organised the workshop titled "Developing skills in the bio-based industries: future bioeconomy pathways" moderated by Davide Viaggi (UNIBO and BIObec coordinator).

4.6 Registration

Registration was centralised through a survey generated in Ms Forms and included in CTA website. All data was managed according to the FAIR principles and good data management practices as well as BIObec ethical guidelines for personal data and recruiting volunteers, which are GDPR compliant, to avoid transferring personal data between partners.

The survey collected the following information from the registers:

- First and last name.
- E-mail address.
- City.
- Type of institution (academy, public administration, private sector or other).
- Name of the institution.

In the survey, it was also indicated if registrants wanted to subscribe to the BIObec newsletter in the future, as well as a reminder that the full session would be recorded to be included as an e-learning material.

4.7 Required equipment, support material and logistics

Two rounds of e-mails were performed the week before and the day of the event with all the registrants. In these emails, it was shared the final agenda and the link to the Teams room in which the workshop would be hold. Therefore, a computer with access to internet was enough to follow the workshop.

Each responsible of the session prepared a presentation in PowerPoint (Microsoft Office) that was shared with the participants. In the specific case of the e-learning materials, the responsible shared his own screen and went through the BIObec website showing all the relevant information.

Once the event finished, an email was sent to attendees by CTA including both the link in which all the materials used during the event could be found, and the satisfaction survey (next section). An example of this email is provided below:

“Dear participant,

Thank you so much for joining us during the BIObec capacity building and 2nd International IRWG workshop. [Here](#) you can find the materials used during the event and [here](#) the videos recorded. More information about the BIObec project is also available on our website (<https://biobec.eu/>).

It would be nice if you could answer the following satisfaction survey and provide your feedback about the workshop: [link](#). It would not take you more than five minutes. This information is very important for us to improve upcoming activities.

Best regards,

In order to ensure a high level of dissemination of the material developed for the workshop, it was decided to send also the link to those that registered but did not attend:

“Dear registrants,

Thank you so much for your registration to BIObec Capacity building and 2nd International IRWG workshop. Here [[hyperlink](#)] you can find the materials used during the event. More information about the BIObec project is also available on our website (<https://biobec.eu/>).

Best regards,”

The videos of the workshop can be found here:: <https://biobec.eu/e-learning-materials/#tab-4> and the presentations here: <https://biobec.eu/documents/>

4.8 Satisfaction survey

Once the event was completed, hosts gathered feedback from the attendees in order to assess the success of the action and to learn about attendees' expectations, potential overlooks that might have occurred or tentative improvements that might be considered in further events.

An example of the satisfaction survey template prepared can be found in annex 3. The Satisfaction survey was prepared in Ms forms and uploaded to CTA website.

5. Results

5.1 Potential attendees

Due to privacy concerns, the BIObec project does not have a general email address list to contact potential attendees to the workshop. In order to avoid uncertainty, it was decided by the consortium to generate a list of contacted institutions. The collaborative effort of the BIObec consortium has reported more than 140 personal contacts to different institutions that are representatives from the quadruple helix (Annex 1)

As an example of the dissemination performed, CTA generated 4 posts on Twitter, 2 posts on LinkedIn and its insertion in two CTA newsletters. CTA has a strong positioning on Twitter and LinkedIn with more than 6660 and 6800 followers respectively and more than 6600 newsletter subscribers.

5.2 Registration

The registration of participants was centralised through a Ms Forms hosted on CTA website, which allowed us to analyse the geographical spread of the workshop and the type of professionals reached. We received a total of 69 registrations. In order to avoid bias during the analysis of the data those registrants directly involved in the implementation of BIObec project were removed, giving a final number of 57 individuals (Figure 2).

Figure 2-. Data analysis of initial registrants

Due to the nature of the project, an overrepresentation of EU countries was expected as well as of those countries directly related with the Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs). Although, we got an overrepresentation of registrants related to academia (40%), we could also reach the private and the public sectors (19%). In addition, the 21% of people in the category “other” represents clusters, associations and even citizens. From this analysis, we can conclude that the channels and the method to reach potential attendees were designed properly.

5.3 Attendees

The total number of participants to the workshop was 56 participants (Annex 2). In order to make a proper analysis of the data, we have again removed the participants directly involved in the implementation of BIObec project. In this case the total number is 35 individuals (Figure 3).

Figure 3-. Data analysis of participants

The reduction in the number of participants is in the line with other events previously organised within the framework of BIObec project. The geographical location of participants is directly linked to the BIObec partners. The main sector represented is the educational (40%), followed by public administration (23%). Unfortunately, the private sector was significantly reduced when compared to the list of registrants. In addition, the category “other” (20%) represents clusters, associations, and citizens. In general, we can conclude that the level of engagement of individuals not directly linked to BIObec is close to 60% (number of participants /number of registrants).

5.4 Day description

Davide Viaggi (UNIBO), coordinator of the BIObec project, opened the workshops by welcoming the participants and presenting the project. He highlighted the main objectives of each workshop: on the one hand, the presentation of the BIObec methodology through the roadmap that has been developed and the e-learning materials that support the methodology, and on the other hand, the revision of the exploitable assets that are ready to be implemented by the educational community.

Rafael Dueñas-Sánchez (CTA), as one of the roadmap developers, reminded the participants that the workshop would be recorded and introduced the BIObec project to the participants in detail (Figure 4). He highlighted the objectives of the project and briefly described what a Bio-Based Education Centre is from the consortium's point of view. He summarised the initial methodology used by the consortium to theoretically create the BBECs. He recapitulated the main features of the six pilot BBECs and highlighted the lessons learnt, particularly in terms of the main advantages and disadvantages identified by the consortium.

Figure 4-. Rafael Dueñas Sánchez during the presentation of the capacity building section.

The roadmap was then presented to the audience, showing how the original methodology had been evolved. In the current version, the roadmap has become an iterative and superposing methodology over 5 stages, incorporating the knowledge accumulated during the project implementation (D4.2). After a detailed step-by-step explanation, he presented the basis for the development of a self-assessment tool that presents the information in a more user-friendly manner. This is based on the identification of the actions to be taken in an online survey that indicates the maturity

level of the proposed centre and where a putative BBEC developer can find the key information.

Daniel Matilla (SIE), as responsible for the creation of the e-learning materials, showed “in vivo” where the different materials can be found on the BIObec website (<https://biobec.eu>). Daniel went through the e-learning materials section, showing the interactive tools that have been created to help people better understanding on BIObec results. These materials include maps with basic information about each BBEC, interactive story maps, interviews with the BBEC leaders, as well as videos of the workshops and webinars hold during the project implementation (Figure 5).

Figure 5-. Daniel Matilla showing the e-learning materials.

As part of the 2nd IRWG international workshop, Selenia Marinelli (FVA), WP5 leader and main responsible of the development of the BIObec exploitation plan, presented an overview of the main assets and tools from the BIObec results, that could be exploited by stakeholders.

In this regard, the identified assets are grouped into 5 different categories: studies and analyses; assessment tools methodologies and frameworks; network creation and stakeholder engagement; and replicable formats and educational tools. In the end, these categories included 18 assets that are ready to be used in the implementation of new BBEC structures, if desired. Selenia reviewed the key assets, indicating what they are, what they are useful for, and finally, where the information can be found (Figure 6).

Implementation and replication working group (IRWG)

Creation of the IRWG

The stakeholders participating to BIObec IRWG designed the multi-level BBECs, by providing their **expectations, needs, requirements, opportunities and barriers**, getting first hand insights with regards to the setup of bioeconomy education centres and **having direct access to good practices and case studies in different European Countries mapped by BIObec.**

Engagement

They have been **engaged in the co-design of the BBECs in 6 European Areas**, tailoring the format to respond to the different regions' specificities (local, regional, national) with dedicated workshops at regional and International levels.

Exploitation

In the last months of the project, IRWG members are even more **central to make sure that BIObec project's outcomes will be actionable in their context, considering present and future needs** of the industry and of the surrounding ecosystem at local, regional, national and/or international levels.

Selenia Marinelli (Guest)

Figure 6-. Selenia Marinelli during the presentation of the 2nd International IRWG section.

Finally, Davide Viaggi (UNIBO) opened a round of questions, giving the participants the opportunity to interact with comments or questions. In general, the participants asked about where they could find the information regarding the project, and they showed general satisfaction on the content as well.

As it was indicated previously, the workshops were recorded and included as e-learning materials (D4.4), as foreseen in the DoA. The videos of the workshops can be found here: <https://biobec.eu/e-learning-materials/#tab-4> and the presentations here: <https://biobec.eu/documents/>

5.5 Satisfaction survey

After the completion of the workshop, a satisfaction survey was sent to the external participants (not BIObec partners). The survey structure can be checked in the annex 3. The survey was answered by the 17% of the participants to the workshop and showed in general a high degree of satisfaction as well as in the completeness of the different sections (Figure 7).

Figure 7-. Radar chart with score per participant.

In average, the categories were scored with more than 4.5 points (Annex 4). The survey also asked by the how they hear about the event, 66% indicated by direct invitation showing that this method is the most effective way to engage stakeholders to attend the workshop.

6. Conclusions

The BIObec project has successfully developed a comprehensive approach to multi-level Bio-Based Education Centres to meet the current and future needs of the industry, considering local, regional, national and international contexts. Through the initiation of six pilot BBECs strategically located across Europe, the project has provided detailed designs, economic and financial assessments, and governance plans among others.

In particular, WP4 focused on providing a roll-out strategy and roadmap for coordinating the replication of BBECs at the European and international levels. Task 4.3, within WP4, aimed to transfer the BIObec methodology for implementing regional BBECs to external regions. As part of this task, a capacity building workshop was organised, the details of which are described in this report.

While the initial plan for the workshop underwent modifications, the consortium successfully moved to an online format, ensuring wider participation, and mitigating the challenges associated with in-person events. By organising in the same day the capacity building workshop (WP4) and the 2nd international IRWG workshop (WP5), the consortium aimed to maximise synergies and provide a holistic view of the project outcomes.

The workshops attracted a diverse audience, including stakeholders from academia, public administration, and the private sector, as well as representatives from clusters and associations. Through intensive work of the consortium partners, mainly by personal invitation and supported by social media dissemination, posting on digital platforms and promotion at key events, the consortium effectively reached a broad audience interested in the bioeconomy field.

In general, the workshop achieved its objectives of supporting the replication and roll-out of BIObec outputs in external regions and recording the event for inclusion in the e-learning materials. Moreover, the organisation back-to-back with the exploitable assets and tools complements the transfer methodology by providing a practical perspective on the implementation process. Feedback from participants indicated a high level of satisfaction with the content and organisation of the workshop.

In conclusion, the BIObec capacity building and 2nd international IRWG workshops provided a general overview of the results developed in WP4, generated synergies with the WP5 and finally capacitated participants for the replication of BBECs in external regions through the experience gained during the implementation of the BIObec project.

Annexes

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Annex 1 Contacted institutions

Aarhus Universitet (AU)	Cleantech Cluster	Instituto Interamericano de Cooperación para la Agricultura	Sectoral Competence Council Material Recovery Sector
Aborgase	Climate Change Centre Austria	Instituto Universitario de investigación desarrollo regional (UGR)	Skive College S/I
Acesur	Consejería de agricultura, pesca, agua y desarrollo rural. Junta de Andalucía	Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Olivar y Aceite de Oliva de la Universidad de Jaén (INUO)	Skive Kommune
ACIB	Cooperativa San Isidro de Loxa	Ireland Department of Agriculture Food and Marine	Smallops
Agencia Andaluza del Conocimiento	Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de Andalucía	Ireland Department of Environment Climate and Communications	SOIL O-LIVE PROJECT (UJA)
Agro Sevilla	Council for Competences in the Water, Wastewater Management and Reclamation Sector	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation	Southern Regional Assembly
ALTER Capital	Cuatrecasas, Gonçalves Pereira S.L.P	Irish Rural Link /CAP Network Ireland	Teagasc
Andaltec	Dcoop	Ital Biotech	TEPRO
Andaltec Centro Tecnológico del Plástico	DNT non woven fabrics	Jagiellonian University	TRAGSATEC
APRE	ECOGESTIONA	Jordbrugets UddannelsesCenter Århus	UJA
Arla Foods	Ecoplus	JRC - Knowledge Center for Bioeconomy	Umweltbundesamt
Asociación Española Agricultura de Conservación Suelos Vivos	ECOTERRAE	Karelia University of Applied Sciences	Umweltministerium
Axon Partners group	Erhvervsakademi Dania, Grenaa	Klimafonden Skive	Unibio A/S
Beonnat-El Jarpil	ERINN	Københavns Universitet (KU)	Unión de Consumidores de Andalucía (UCAUCE)
Biat Group	EU CAP Network	Lazio Innova	Unitelma
BioBASE GmbH	European Forest Institute	Lenzing AG	Universidad de Almería
BIObeo	FH Kufstein Tirol	Mar Océana	Universidad de Córdoba
Bioliza	FH Salzburg, Campus Kuchl	Mercantec	Universidad de Granada

Biopharma Research, SA	Finnish Environmental Institute Syke	Ministry of Education	Universidad de Jaén
Bundesforschungszentrum für Wald - Forstliche Ausbildungsstätte Traunkirchen	Finnish Forest Centre	Mondi Paper	Universidad de Sevilla
Bundesministerium für Landwirtschaft	FPDual	MULTISCAN	University of Agriculture in Cracow
Business Joensuu	Fundación Circe	NATAC	University of Bari
Bygholm Landbrugsskole	FVG Cluster Agrifood	Natural Resources Institute Finland Luke	University of Sapienza
CASI	galisteo asesores	Ökosoziales Forum	University of Teramo
CEIPES	GRUPO EMPRESARIAL LA CAÑA S.L	Onimagin Technologies SCA	University of Turin
Centro Tecnológico Andaltec	HBLFA Raumberg-Gumpenstein	PBio	Vestjyllands Anel A.M.B.A.
CEPSA	Healthy Food Ibérica (VERDEO)	PLANTAS CONTINENTAL, S.A.	VIA University College (Professionshøjskolen)
CERTH	ICOS Skillnet	Polish Federation of Food Producers Employers' Association	Viborg Kommune
CESIE	IFAPA	Polish Waterworks Chamber of Commerce	Vicerrectorado Investigación Universitario of Jaén
Chimica Verde Bionet	IFAPA - Andalusian Institute for Agricultural, Fisheries, Food and Ecological Production Research and Training	Regional Council of North Karelia	West Pomeranian Chemical Cluster Green Chemistry
CIDAF	Impact Hub Málaga	Representatives from Apulia Region	WoodKplus Kompetenzzentrum Holz GmbH
CIRC BIO Research Group MTU	Innosuns	Ressourcenforum Austria	Zagolive
CIRCE	InnovaWood	Riveria Vocational School	ZSI
Circular Engineering (spin off UJA)	Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, CSIC y US	Roskilde Universitet (RUC)	
CIVITTA	Instituto de Investigaciones Químicas - Universidad de Sevilla	Sector Council for Competences High-quality Food	

Annex 2 List of participants

	Country	City	Private sector
Participant 1	Italy	Rome	Private sector
Participant 2	Italy	Rome	Private sector
Participant 3	Spain	Malaga	Academy
Participant 4	Spain	Sevilla	Private non profit
Participant 5	Spain	Madrid	Private sector
Participant 6	Spain	Sevilla	Private non profit
Participant 7	Spain	Huelva	Academy
Participant 8	Spain	Sevilla	Private non profit
Participant 9	Italy	Bologna	Academy
Participant 10	Spain	Zaragoza	Private sector
Participant 11	Italy	Rome	Private sector
Participant 12	Poland	Warsaw	Public administration
Participant 13	Poland	Kielce	NGO
Participant 14	Denmark	Aarhus	Cluster
Participant 15	Italy	Bologna	Academy
Participant 16	Finland	Joensuu	Academy
Participant 17	Spain	Madrid	Private sector
Participant 18	Poland	Warsaw	NGO
Participant 19	Bulgaria	Sofia	Public administration
Participant 20	Germany	Jülich	Academy
Participant 21	Spain	Sevilla	Academy
Participant 22	Spain	Sevilla	Public administration
Participant 23	Germany	Irdning-Donnersbachtal	Academy
Participant 24	Ireland	Dublin	Public administration
Participant 25	Spain	Sevilla	Public administration
Participant 26	Finland	Kristinestad	Municipal development co,
Participant 27	Ireland	Tralee	Academy
Participant 28	Undefined	Undefined	Academy
Participant 29	Spain	Jaen	Academy
Participant 30	Germany	Hohenheim	Academy
Participant 31	Spain	Sevilla	Academy
Participant 32	Spain	Madrid	Private sector
Participant 33	Italy	Bologna	Innovation Cluster
Participant 34	France	Reims	Public administration
Participant 35	Spain	Cordoba	Academy

Participant 36	Poland	Warsaw	Public administration
Participant 37	Italy	Bologna	Academy
Participant 38	Italy	Rome	Association
Participant 39	Italy	Bologna	Academy
Participant 40	Ireland	Dublin	Public administration
Participant 41	Undefined	Undefined	Undefined
Participant 42	Undefined	Undefined	Undefined
Participant 43	Romania	Bucharest	Academy
Participant 44	Spain	Almeria	Private sector
Participant 45	Italy	Bologna	Academy
Participant 46	Spain	Cadiz	Nominal
Participant 47	Poland	Kielce	Public administration
Participant 48	Undefined	Undefined	Undefined
Participant 49	Austria	St. Pölten	Intermediary
Participant 50	Ireland	Kilkenny	Academy
Participant 51	Croatia	Zagreb	Academy
Participant 52	Poland	Krakow	Academy
Participant 53	Italy	Itala	Private sector
Participant 54	Germany	Bonn	NGO
Participant 55	Bulgaria	Sofia	Public administration
Participant 56	Austria	Vienna	Academy

Annex 3 Satisfaction survey

With the aim of gathering information about your experience at the **BIObec Capacity Building and 2nd International IRWG workshop**, we have created this survey. Your input will help us in the planning and implement future activities.

This survey will not take more than 5 minutes of your time. Thank you very much for your collaboration.

Please, evaluate the following aspects of the event:

- Organisation *
From 1 star (Poor) to 5 stars (Excellent)
- Relevance of the topic and content *
From 1 star (Poor) to 5 stars (Excellent)
- Completeness of the presentation of BIObec replication methodology *
From 1 star (Poor) to 5 stars (Excellent)
- Completeness the presentation of the e-learning material*
From 1 star (Poor) to 5 stars (Excellent)
- Completeness the presentation of exploitable assets *
From 1 star (Poor) to 5 stars (Excellent)
- Level of satisfaction with the workshop in general *
From 1 star (Poor) to 5 stars (Excellent)
- Where did you hear about this event?
 - Social Media
 - Newsletter
 - Direct invitation
 - Other: ...
- Please, write below any comment or feedback you may have about the workshop.

Thank you!

Annex 4 Results of satisfaction survey

	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4	Participant 5	Participant 6	Average
Organisation	4	4	5	5	5	5	4.7
Relevance of the topic and content	5	5	4	5	5	3	4.5
Completeness of BIObec replication methodology	5	5	4	5	5	3	4.5
Completeness of the e-learning material	5	5	4	5	5	5	4.8
Completeness of exploitable assets	5	5	3	5	5	4	4.5
Satisfaction with the workshop in general	5	5	4	5	5	4	4.7
How did you hear about this event?	Direct invitation	Other	Direct invitation	Direct invitation	Newsletter	Direct invitation	NA
Please, write below any comment or feedback you may have about the workshop	NA°	NA	NA	Very good and professional event!	NA	NA	NA

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